

EUROPEAN MOUNTAIN AREA ENTREPRENEURSHIP. CASE STUDY OF THE ROMANIAN FINANCIAL, INSURANCE AND REAL ESTATE ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

In the current pandemic context, the business sector present significant damages. In order to recalibrate the European economy, the paper propose servitization applied to mountain entrepreneurship, because this concept fits perfectly into the new global pandemic context. As example, the paper present the Population of active enterprises in the European mountain area for Financial, insurance and real estate activities excluding holding companies. As a case study, the article analyses entrepreneurship in the North-East region of Romania. The paper introduces two hypotheses: H0 (the null) - the probability of recession across an industry is not positively correlated with the central tendencies (regress) or H1 (the alternative) - the probability of recession across an industry is positively correlated with the central tendencies (increase). The conclusions show that for the case study the recession across an industry is positively correlated with the central tendencies. The article contains key concepts as mountain entrepreneurship, business sector and servitization. Methods of the paper are proposing the analysis of the descriptive statistics combined with exploratory research. The article contains results for the analysis of an emergent sector for European mountain and North-East region of Romania. The conclusions point that in order to realize the true potential of servitization, the business sector needs to plan for digital transformation.

Keywords: *mountain entrepreneurship, servitization, business sector*

INTRODUCTION

In the current pandemic context, business models, international/national/regional/local level, must be reshaped and rethought through the eye of servitization. E-supply chain management systems are the inflexion point of the operations and business models (Barrad, S., & Valverde, R., 2020). Under these conditions, sustainable entrepreneurship through servitization is the appropriate solution for relaunching the world economy, as well as national and regional ones, especially from mountain area. Sustainable, mountain, entrepreneurship implies the existence of important coordinates, including servitization (this present interest for the current research). "Servitization and Industry 4.0 are considered two of the latest trends in the industrial transformation of companies. Servitization is mainly focused on value-added for customers (demand-pull) while Industry 4.0 is frequently linked to the added value given by the manufacturing process (technology-push)." (Frank/Mendes/Ayala/Ghezzi 2019: p.1)

The paper present the population of active enterprise from the mountain area across the Europe and analyse the North-East region of Romania (34 GDP / c%) because is one the poorest from Europe, together with Severozapaden from Bulgaria (29 GDP / c%), Mayotte from France (32 GDP / c%), Severen Tsentralen and Yuzhen Tsentralen from Bulgaria (33 GDP / c% each) (Eurostat). In this context, sustainable entrepreneurship in Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, presently Romania, represent a must. CEE countries offers all the possibilities in developing sustainable entrepreneurship through servitization.

The paper analyze Financial, insurance and real estate activities that could represent the subject of the fourth industrial revolution and servitization in some European mountains area, especially from the North-East region of Romania.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

At present, the services of sustainable entrepreneurship must be seen as a continuation of industry, but also industry as a continuation of services. In fact, the fourth industrial revolution is perfectly applicable to the servitude that is a part of Industry 4.0. Currently, "companies are reconsidering their offers by moving from terms such as "goods or services" to the package of "goods + services + support + knowledge + self-service." (Kowalkowski, C., Gebauer, H., Kamp, B., & Parry, G., 2017: p. 4). The concept of services indicates to applications, offers or applications. The terms "service infusion" (Brax 2005; Kowalkowski / Kindström / Alejandro / Brege / Biggemann 2012), "servitude" (Vandermerwe / Rada 1988), and "transition to services" (Fang / Palmatier / Steenkamp 2008; Oliva / Kallenberg 2003) are used to show the growth of service applications ... Servitization is defined as a transformational process of change from the production-centered to the approach-centered logic and business model." (Kowalkowski / Gebauer / Kamp / Parry 2017: p. 7).

There are many factories in the CEE countries, especially in Romania that present a encouraging position in this regard, from the perspective of pointing on servitization and Industry 4.0. Even if there are statements affirming that it is not possible to jump from Industry 2.0 to 4.0, EEC countries, especially Romania, will benefit considerably from the fourth wave of industry and will attract many investments in this regard. The Romanian socio-economic context, especially the mountain ones, has advantages for the transition to Industry 4.0 and servitization, as follows Industry 4.0 strategy proposes to bring to Europe, especially on customized production, high quality and customer-centered manufacturing. CEE countries are favorable destinations for investment in innovative production facilities, especially in real estate. (Costache, A.G./Barliba, D.M./Zaleschi, V. C./Cotet, G. B./Cotet E. 2017: p. 204; Popescu, D./Amza, C., 2017: p. 50)

Methods of the paper are proposing the analysis of the descriptive statistics combined with exploratory research. The hypothesis are focused on developing the entrepreneurship in financial industry from European mountains area and from North-East region of Romania (Covaci M. 2009; Covaci M. 2017; Covaci M. 2019), clusterization of the developed/emergent *Financial, insurance and real estate activities excluding holding companies*. Data has been prelucrated according to Eurostat, in Excel and SPSS. The standard analyzed period is 2008-2016.

The central tendency for *Financial, insurance and real estate activities excluding holding companies* in the analyzed period, amounting to 2074.25 (average), shows that the north-eastern population of the active enterprises for the established sector increased from 1690 (2008) to 2613 (2015).

As seen, this sector have increase in numbers of population of active enterprises. Thus, this industries represent a potential for sustainable entrepreneurship in the North-East region of Romania.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Regarding business sector, one of the most valuable indicator is Population of active enterprises in t – number. For the analyzed sector, *Financial, insurance and real estate activities excluding holding companies*, this indicator present important increases to some European mountains are between 2008-2016, as follow Bulgaria by 75,33%, Spain 25,69%, Italy 20,30%, Austria 19,47%, Romania 68,82%, and Slovakia 65,15%. Only Portugal present a decrease of -6,86%.

Table 1

Population of active enterprises for *Financial, insurance and real estate activities excluding holding companies* at the European mountain area level

GEO/TIME	2008	2009	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Bulgaria	9.941	13.999	14.705	14.899	15.376	16.047	16.718	17.430
Czechia	:	:	:	:	12.864	9.821	9.388	9.514
Spain	136.125	138.281	140.964	143.151	143.664	152.191	:	171.098
France	:	:	54.201	:	:	62.942	65.082	67.503
Croatia	:	:	1.951	1.740	1.625	1.499	1.510	1.742
Italy	125.231	132.848	142.837	144.452	148.277	147.492	147.575	150.656
Austria	11.864	12.280	12.577	13.187	17.624	15.032	14.578	14.174
Poland	:	:	:	:	:	:	:	5.704
Portugal	10.461	10.114	9.912	9.666	9.471	9.122	9.473	9.743
Romania	5.242	5.373	3.806	6.031	7.358	7.404	7.259	8.850
Slovakia	6.491	6.545	9.465	8.996	6.990	8.684	10.316	10.720

Source: Author processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

Statistics for the North-East region of Romania presents for Financial and Insurance Activities; real estate activities sector (figures 1 - panels a, b, c, d) an average of 2074.25 with a standard error of 189450, 95% confidence interval with a lower limit of 1626.27 and an upper limit of 2522.23, average mean value 5% of 2081.72, median of 1943.50, variance of 287130.500, standard deviation of 535.846, minimum of 1299, maximum of 2715, simple interval of 1416, interquartile range of 955, correctness of 0.046 with a standard error of 0.752, Kurtosis of -1.649 with a standard error of 1.481.

At a first analysis, the distribution curve is relatively symmetrically central, and the scores around the average are very concentrated, with the appearance of leptocurticity, although the distribution is unimodal. (figure 1a)

Working hypothesis: the distribution of scores is considered normal and, therefore, parametric tests will be applied. The extreme values of the distribution, although they are in very small numbers, change the appearance of the histogram, by inducing a positive asymmetry, being still clinically important. The concentration of a large number of scores around the average ($M = 2074.25$) produces a certain leptocurticity of the distribution, due to the related phenomena in the Romanian economy. The logarithm of the values obtained, according to the universally accepted statistical rules, allowed to balance the distribution according to the normal Gauss-Laplace curve.

The normal Q-Q plot test, after logarithm, shows a distribution of real scores around normal values, represented by the oblique line in the graph, which corresponds to a normal distribution. (figure 1b).

Fig. 1. Financial and Insurance Activities sectors; real estate activities. Source: Author processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

The Q-Q detrended plot test, on the dispersion of empirical scores to normal, represented by the right with the score $z = 0$ for the mean and standard deviation 1, after logarithm, shows that they fall within a standard deviation, corresponding to a normal distribution. By logarithm, the scores obtained were subjected to statistical processing, after which all the factors involved in the study were taken into account, in order to obtain data as

close as possible to the reality recorded in the North-East region of Romania, even if the measures taken in the economy they unbalanced the distribution of scores for a short period of time (figure 1c).

The importance of these tests is given by the need to carefully observe the influences of certain factors in the evolution of the sectors Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities. Following the application of normality tests, after logarithmization, the null hypothesis must be rejected and the working hypothesis can be analyzed. The descriptive and inferential analysis will be done considering the distribution of scores within normal limits, according to the working hypothesis, for which the parametric tests are applied. (figure 1d)

CONCLUSIONS

Servitization is a great opportunity for Romania, but market players do not yet understand the power of this desideratum. Romanian companies, but especially central / regional / local administrations, should figure out the importance and emergency of digitization, with success and bankruptcy occurring at high speeds.

Sector that should be attached firstly to servitization in Romania is *Financial, insurance and real estate activities excluding holding companies*.

For *Financial, insurance and real estate activities excluding holding companies*, the statistics and information in the figures confirm the high agglomeration and the development trend of this sector in the northeastern region of Romania. During the analyzed period, the hypothesis H1 (intensification of activity) was verified, the frequency having a total variation of 2.9 - from 0.1 to 3. Statistics confirm the intensification of the growth rate of this sector.

The major growth of the population of active enterprises in the presented sectors are correlated with a strong drawing of the North-Eastern region of Romania economy. The influence of clusterization and involvement of the academic environment in the North-East region of Romania and European funding to this specific industry must be considerable. (Covaci B./Suciu/Covaci M 2018; Covaci M. 2014; Covaci B. 2019)

To realize the true potential of servitization, companies from CEE, especially from Romania, needs to plan for digital transformation. (T&T Plus 2016)

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